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Corrigendum: The credibility challenge for global fluvial flood risk analysis (2016 *Environ. Res. Lett.* [11 094014](#))

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The formula in the article for Model Agreement Index is incorrect. It has an extra N in the denominator that should not be there. The correct formulae for the Model Agreement Index is shown below.

$$\text{MAI} = \frac{\sum_{i=2}^N \frac{i}{N} a_i}{A} \quad (1)$$

The analyses presented in the paper were conducted with the correct formula.

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